

Impact on the Emotional Intelligence among Female Nurses in Multi-Speciality Hospitals at Southern Chennai

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Abstract

Aims': Emotional intelligence (EI) has been extensively studied in workplace setting. In the nursing field, however, the research data is limited. The study aimed to estimate the EI of nursing personnel in multi-speciality hospital in southern Chennai, determine which factor were associated with EI, and examine how EI correlated with the emotional intelligence dimensions (i.e., use of emotional, self-emotional appraisal, regulation of emotion and other emotional appraisal).

Study Design: Multi stage stratified random sampling.

Place and Duration of Study: The population under examination was derived from a reference population of nursing staff working in multi-speciality hospital in southern Chennai between April and May of 2018.

Methodology: A total of 300 nurses completed the Law, Wong and song 2004 scale consisting of 16 items measuring four basic emotional dimensions use of emotional, self-emotional appraisal, regulation of emotion and other emotional appraisal. As well as questions regarding demographic, socioeconomic and occupational characteristics.

Results: The EI total mean score was 35.51. The nurses aged 38 to 47 years hold had the highest EI scores ($p=0.003$), experience ($p=0.00$) educational qualification ($p=0.002$) with a positive effect on the EI among nurses to serving in hospitals.

Conclusion: The present study revealed the need for interventions and improvement in emotional intelligence ability in clinical nurses in multi-speciality hospital in southern Chennai. EI scores and conformed positive relationship with the emotional dimensions of nurses.

Keywords: emotional intelligence: female nurses: multi-speciality hospital: southern Chennai.

Introduction

Emotional disorders, such as depression, anxiety and stress, constitute the most common diseases of this century, despite the improvement in technology and the subsequent benefits it has offered. The professional environment plays a significant role in the physical state of the individual. Particular the hospital environment is extremely stressful due to tis specific peculiarities.

Nursing personnel are regarded as a professional team with increased stress anxiety and depression due to their daily routine, which is particularly demanding since they are forced to cope with pain, sadness and death. Nurses cope with the emotional needs of the patients and their families, and the fact that many of their tasks are tides.

EI is perceived as a new relevant concept that has appeared in the literature over the past few decades. However, according to Goleman its origins stem from antiquity with Aristotle, who studied the value of emotions in the field of interpersonal relationships. EI in the nursing field is considered to be particularly important for the existence and understanding of emotions. Emotions play a central role in the ability of individuals to understand and assimilate emotional processes. Emotionally Intelligent nurses can manage their thoughts and feelings in harmony.

Emotional Intelligence

“Emotional Intelligence (EI) is the ability to acquire and apply knowledge from your emotions and the emotions of others”. You can use the information about what you are feeling to help you make effective decisions about what to say or do (or not to say or do) next. Byron Stock (2007).

Need for Study

Emotional Intelligence is a very important factor which improves the quality of individual life. It promotes intra personal relationship, Inter Personal relationships, adaptability, stress tolerance and general mood influences work performance among female nurses working in multi-speciality hospitals.

Objectives of the Study

- To assess the level of EI among nurses in selected hospitals.
- To assess the factors influencing EI among nurses working in selected hospitals.
- To find the association between the study findings with selected demographic variables of samples.

Hypotheses of the study

H1: A statistically significant relationship exists between age and EI among nurses.

H2: A statistically significant relationship exists between experience and EI among nurses.

H3: A statistically significant relationship exists between educational qualification and EI among nurses.

Materials and Methods

1. Research design

A stratified random sampling method was conducted between April and May of 2018, to investigate the effects of EI (Independent variable) on the emotional dimensions (Dependent variable) of nurses employed in multi-speciality hospitals in southern Chennai. Statistical tools used for measuring EI-demographic variables-female nurses. A test used for measuring mean SD, F-test and one-way ANOVA was used to compare the mean scores between groups (EI associations with the demographic and work characteristic). In addition to the above, the statistical data was processed with SPSS ver.22 and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

2. Research Instruments

Self-completed questionnaires were used for the data collection, were of high reliability and validity. Law, Wong and Song 2004 scale consisting of 16 items measuring four basic emotional dimensions use of emotional, self-emotional appraisal, regulation of emotion and other emotional

appraisal. The use of emotion for the solution of problems. The items were scored based on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. Reliability coefficients using Cronbach's alpha in the original validation study for the fore dimensions ranged between 0.85 to 0.83.

3. Participants

The population under examination was derived from a reference population of female nurses working in multi-specialty hospitals in southern Chennai. A representative sample of nurses from (multi-speciality hospitals- mount, vadapalani, R.R., C.S.I.Kalyani, Sri Chakra, Grace, Kavitha, COSH, Deepam). The sample size was determined according to the desired level for the accuracy of the results the financial cost and the time available.

Results

The sample size (N) consisted of a total of 300 individuals and their demographic variables are shown in the following tables. The EI total mean score was 35.51. The nurses aged 38 to 47 years hold had the highest EI scores ($p=0.003$), experience ($p=0.00$) educational qualification ($p=0.002$) with a positive effect on the EI among nurses to serving in hospitals.

Table 1

Emotional intelligence dimensions	Age	N	Mean	SD	F value	p value
Use of emotional	Between 18-27 years	174	3.51	0.63	1.332	0.266
	Between 28-37 years	115	3.60	0.74		
	Between 38-47 years	11	3.31	0.25		
	Total	300	3.54	0.66		
Self-emotional appraisal	Between 18-27 years	174	2.81	0.55	6.111	0.003**
	Between 28-37 years	115	3.05	0.64		
	Between 38-47 years	11	2.75	0.40		
	Total	300	2.90	0.59		
Regulation of emotion	Between 18-27 years	174	2.97	0.63	9.309	0.000**
	Between 28-37 years	115	2.70	0.48		
	Between 38-47 years	11	2.56	0.53		
	Total	300	2.85	0.59		
Other emotional appraisal	Between 18-27 years	174	2.59	0.48	3.008	0.051
	Between 28-37 years	115	2.51	0.50		
	Between 38-47 years	11	2.27	0.24		
	Total	300	2.55	0.48		

Table 2

Emotional intelligence dimensions	Age	N	Mean	SD	F value	p value
Use of emotional	Below 5	183	3.51	0.63	0.434	0.729
	Between 6-10	93	3.60	0.78		
	Between 11-15	23	3.50	0.40		
	Between 16-20	1	3.52	0.00		
	Total	300	3.54	0.66		

Self-emotional appraisal	Below 5	183	2.88	0.54	1.122	0.34
	Between 6-10	93	2.91	0.67		
	Between 11-15	23	3.06	0.59		
	Between 16-20	1	2.21	0.00		
	Total	300	2.90	0.59		
Regulation of emotion	Below 5	183	2.95	0.60	7.848	0.000**
	Between 6-10	93	2.76	0.53		
	Between 11-15	23	2.46	0.43		
	Between 16-20	1	1.74	0.00		
	Total	300	2.85	0.59		
Other emotional appraisal	Below 5	183	2.56	0.49	0.576	0.631
	Between 6-10	93	2.56	0.48		
	Between 11-15	23	2.42	0.38		
	Between 16-20	1	2.39	0.00		
	Total	300	2.55	0.48		

Table 3

Emotional intelligence dimensions	Age	N	Mean	SD	F value	p value
Use of emotional	B.Sc Nursing	159	3.51	0.56	5.021	0.000**
	GNM	122	3.50	0.76		
	B.com	1	2.56	0.00		
	M.Sc Nursing	9	4.32	0.40		
	Diam	3	3.12	0.30		
	CAN	6	4.26	0.30		
	Total	300	3.54	0.66		
Self-emotional appraisal	B.Sc Nursing	159	2.85	0.46	3.795	0.002**
	GNM	122	2.91	0.72		
	B.com	1	2.26	0.00		
	M.Sc Nursing	9	3.28	0.09		
	Diam	3	2.68	0.65		
	CAN	6	3.73	0.05		
	Total	300	2.90	0.59		
Regulation of emotion	B.Sc Nursing	159	2.93	0.54	7.607	0.000**
	GNM	122	2.68	0.60		
	B.com	1	2.00	0.00		
	M.Sc Nursing	9	3.48	0.38		
	Diam	3	2.81	0.09		
	CAN	6	3.54	0.01		
	Total	300	2.85	0.59		

Other emotional appraisal	B.Sc Nursing	159	2.57	0.41	6.9	0.000**
	GNM	122	2.46	0.53		
	B.com	1	1.68	0.00		
	M.Sc Nursing	9	3.21	0.31		
	Diam	3	2.19	0.18		
	CAN	6	2.98	0.07		
	Total	300	2.55	0.48		

**The statistical significances was set at p=0.01. *The statistical significances was set at p=0.05.

Implications

As for implications, since Intra personal relationship, Inter Personal relationships, adoptability, stress tolerance and general mood influence EI, it would be worthwhile for hospital administration and the ministry of health to encourage and enhance the level of EI among multi-speciality hospital female nurses. It is important to assist nurses to develop skills and capable to handle and protect themselves from the effects of work place adversity. Ministry of health should provide more training to nurses developing their EI in their organisation.

Suggestions for further Research

Based on the above conducted F-test and one-way ANOVA. Suggested that multi-speciality hospitals needs to closely monitor towards the level of all factors regarding their Intra personal relationship, Inter Personal relationships, adoptability, stress tolerance and general mood influence among nurses EI will improve their quality of their personal life and work life which will give satisfaction for the nurses.

Conclusion

This study revealed the need for interventions and improvement in emotional intelligence ability in clinical nurses in multi-speciality hospital in southern Chennai. Not only to improve the quality of nurses, but also to protect them from the negative environments on their emotional status.

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